

Vitamin A in Fish Liver Oils.

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A systematic investigation of the vitamin A-potency of Indian fish liver oils does not appear to have been undertaken. Recent observations in other countries on various fish-liver oils including halibut, mackerel and sturgeon liver oils, which have been found to be much more potent in vitamin A than cod liver oil, indicate the possibility of there being large vitamin A reserves in the liver oils of certain Indian fishes also. It is with this possibility in mind that the present investigation was undertaken. We have commenced this work with the liver oils of fishes commonly consumed in Bengal and we expect to send further communications on the subject.

The Assay of Vitamin A in Liver Oils.

The Carr-Price colorimetric method (*Biochem. J.*, 1926, **20**, 497) was adopted for the estimation of vitamin A in the liver oils. Results of the biological tests, which are being carried out, will be reported later.

Within the last few years, however, doubt has been cast on the reliability of the colorimetric method for the assay of vitamin A. Schmidt-Nielsen (*Kon. Norsk. Videnskab. I*, No. 15, 29, 63) has reported that the tintometric and biological tests do not give concordant values for the body and liver oils of certain marine fishes. Ahmad and Drummond (*Biochem. J.*, 1930, **24**, 27), on the other hand, have concluded from a reinvestigation of the subject that for fish oils the tintometric method gives reliable values. Ender (*Biochem. J.*, 1932, **26**, 1118) and Norris (*Bull. Basic. Sci. Res.*, 1931, **3**, 89, 249) have recently given some noteworthy evidence to show that the chromogen concerned is not necessarily identical with vitamin A. Our own results indicate that in the fish liver oils under our investigation, there is probably more than one chromogen present (*cf.* Gillam and Morton, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, **25**, 1346), so that the blue values, we report, should be accepted with reserve as a measure of vitamin A values.

Preparation of the materials.—The finely minced liver was ground up with excess of anhydrous sodium sulphate and extracted repeatedly with ether in the cold. The ethereal extract was evaporated by means of an electric fan and the oil obtained. Generally the oils were coloured, varying from deep yellow to yellow-brown. The oils were fairly mobile, getting more and more viscous on standing. They had their peculiar odours, the smell of *Mrigal* liver oil being strongly suggestive of cod liver oil.

Technique of the colorimetric experiments.—As described by Carr and Price (*loc. cit.*) the liver oil (about 2 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (10 c.c.) dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. 0.4 C.c. of the solution and 4 c.c. of a saturated solution of SbCl_3 in anhydrous chloroform were used for each observation made with a Lovibond tintometer of the B.D.H. pattern. The maximum development of the colour usually took place in about 30 seconds. Matching was always carried out with a standard artificial light.

As intensely deep colours could not be accurately matched, it was found necessary to use very dilute solutions in some cases for tintometric examinations. The relation between the dilution and intensity of colour produced is approximately linear only within a small range. The Carr-Price blue values obtained in this investigation have, however, been computed on the assumption of such a linear relation. The actual deviation from this relation will be observed from the following experiment carried out with *Mrigal* liver oil.

Relation between the dilution of Mrigal liver oil and the intensity of the colour produced.—In Fig. 1, curve (I) shows the relation between the observed colour intensity and the concentration of the liver oil. Curve (II) has been obtained by plotting the Carr-Price values calculated from the respective blue value readings against the concentration of the oil.

It will be seen from curve (I) that the relation between the concentration and the intensity of the colour is linear within a short range and that, where the concentration is relatively higher. At a lower concentration the divergence is very great.

At higher concentrations the C.P. value-concentration curve (Curve II) is parallel to the ordinate which shows that the relation between the concentration and intensity is linear within this range. At lower concentrations the Carr-Price value goes up as high as 500, while the Carr-Price value of the same oil, calculated from readings

FIG. I.

at a higher concentration, is only 216. Thus Carr-Price values obtained from readings at low concentrations are apt to be very misleading.

From these considerations it would seem desirable to observe the blue values of oils at higher concentrations. But the values obtained at these concentrations are generally much above 15 Lovibond units and hence the matching becomes inaccurate. Thus the apparent advantage gained by choosing a concentrated solution for testing is somewhat negated by inaccurate matching.

We have, therefore, accepted a *via media*. The concentration chosen falls roughly within the range where the intensity-concentration relation may be taken to be linear. Within this range the values observed are not too high for accurate matching.

The Blue Values of the Fish Liver Oils.

1. *Halibut liver oil.*—0.6180 G. of the oil dissolved in CHCl_3 gave a very intense coloration with the SbCl_3 reagent, 0.5 c.c. of the chloroform solution was then diluted with chloroform to 10 c.c. so that the final solution contained 0.0309 g. of the oil in 10 c. c.

Obs.	Blue units.	Yellow units.	Neutral tints.
1	9.5	3.4	2
2	9.5	3.5	2
3	9.5	3.5	2
4	9.6	3.5	2
Mean 9.5			

Carr-Price blue value— 614.8.

2. *Rohit (Labeo rohita) liver oil.*—130 G. of fresh *Rohit* liver gave 3.108 g. of a yellowish brown oil. The sample of liver was collected in the earlier part of March. 1.1430 G. of the oil in 10 c.c. chloroform gave a rather intense coloration and 1 c.c. of the above solution was diluted with chloroform so that the solution contained 0.1143 g. of oil in 10 c.c.

Obs.	B	Y	N
1	12.9	4.5	0.4
2	12.9	4.5	0.4
3	12.9	4.5	0.4

Mean 12.9

Carr-Price blue value— 226.6.

Another sample of liver collected in early May gave 5.822 g. of oil from 235 g. of liver. 0.17 G. in 10 c.c. chloroform gave the following values.

Obs.	B	Y	N
1	13.7	2.4	0.2
2	13.7	2.4	0.3
3	13.8	2.4	0.3

Mean 13.7

Carr-Price blue value—161.1.

3. *Mrigal (Cirrhina mrigala) liver oil.*—265 G. of *Mrigal* liver, collected in early May, gave 15.714 g. of a dark brown mobile oil.

0.1663 G. of the oil dissolved in 10 c. c. of chloroform was used for tintometric tests.

Obs.	B	Y	N
1	14.4	2.9	0.4
2	14.4	2.9	0.4
3	14.6	2.9	0.6
4	14.6	3.0	0.6
5	14.7	3.1	0.6

Mean 14.5

Carr-Price blue value— 174.4

4. *Katla (catla catla) liver oil*.—115 G. of *Katla* liver, collected in early May, gave 7.876 g. of a mobile golden yellow oil. 0.2 G. of oil dissolved in 10 c.c. of chloroform was used for tintometric observations.

Obs.	B	Y	N
1	10.2	2.8	0.2
2	11.2	2.9	0.2
3	11.4	2.9	0.3

Mean 10.9

Carr-Price value—109.

5. *Hilsha (Clupea Ilisha) liver oil*.—137 G. of *Hilsha* liver gave 4.213 g. of a golden yellow oil, containing some waxy substance. 0.3 G. of the oil in 10 c.c. of chloroform was used.

Obs.	B	Y	N
1	8.9	2.9	0.7
2	8.8	3.0	0.7
3	9.0	3.0	0.7
4	9.0	3.3	0.7

Mean 8.8

Carr-Price blue value—59.

6. *Vetki (Lates calcarifer) liver oil*.—55 G. of *Vetki* liver gave 1.278 g. of a viscid yellow oil. The sample was collected in late May.

0.05 G. of oil dissolved in 10 c.c. of chloroform gave the following values.

Obs	B	Y	N
1	7.0	2.8	...
2	7.1	2.7	0.1
3	7.1	2.8	0.1
4	7.1	2.9	0.1
Mean 7.1.			

Carr-Price blue value—284.

7. *Cod liver oil*.—1.8 G. of cod liver oil (B.C.P.W.) dissolved in 10 c.c. of chloroform were used. A sample of cod liver oil of Norwegian origin was also tested for vitamin A-potency, 1.9 g. of the oil dissolved in 10 c.c. chloroform being used.

B. C. P. W.			Norwegian.		
Obs.	B	Y	Obs.	B	Y
1	4.0	0.4	1	5	0.7
2	3.9	0.4	2	5	0.8
3	3.9	0.4	3	5	0.8
Mean 3.9			Mean 5.0		

Carr-Price blue value—4.3.

Carr-Price blue value—5.2.

The copious mesenteric fat of *Rohit* was found to be devoid of vitamin A both by tintometric and biological tests.

SUMMARY.

Liver oils of *Rohit*, *Mrigal*, *Katla*, *Vetki* and *Hilsha* fishes have been tested for vitamin A-potency by the tintometric method. Their blue values are of the order of 227, 174, 109, 284 and 59 respectively. Another sample of *Rohit* liver oil, obtained from the liver collected at a different time, gave a blue value of 161, indicating that seasonal variations in vitamin A-content may be considerable. Comparison with two samples of commercial cod liver oil of average activity having blue values of 4.3 and 5.1 indicates the relative richness of the above Indian fish liver oils in vitamin A. The tintometric examination of a sample of halibut liver oil gave a blue value of 614.